

Cellulases and their promising use in tissue engineering and cell sheet technology

Lubica Stankova^{a,*}, Anna Kutova^{b,c,1}, Martina Doubkova^a

^a Laboratory of Biomaterials and Tissue Engineering, Institute of Physiology of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Vídeňská 1083, 142 00 Prague 4, Czech Republic

^b Department of Solid State Engineering, University of Chemistry and Technology, Technická 5, 166 28 Prague 6, Czech Republic

^c Institute of Physics of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Na Slovance 2, 182 21 Prague 8, Czech Republic

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ABSTRACT

Bacterial nanocellulose (BNC) was used to generate continuous scaffold-free sheets of human keratinocytes (HaCaT) after degradation by cellulase from *Trichoderma reesei*. First, we successfully grafted acidic cellulase from *Trichoderma reesei* onto a BNC nanostructure and prepared degradable BNC that dissolved in phosphate-buffered saline within one week. In addition, we selected a cellulase solution that degrades BNC within three hours under physiological conditions. HaCaTs were cultured on four different BNC samples: air-dried (BNC_AD), lyophilized (BNC_L) and plasma-modified (PM) BNC exposed to a direct current Ar⁺ plasma discharge (BNC_AD_PM and BNC_L_PM). On days 1 and 3, the cells were stained with the LIVE/DEAD viability/cytotoxicity kit. The significantly highest cell number on day 3 was found on the BNC_AD_PM membrane (median 65,025 cells/cm²), similar to the standard cell culture polystyrene (median 58,553 cells/cm²). Cell viability on day 3 was greater than 90 % for all samples except BNC_L (62 %). Cell island formation was also preferentially observed on BNC_AD_PM samples. The significant positive effect of PM on cell growth was shown after BNC degradation on day 10 after cell seeding, when continuous sheets of viable keratinocytes were separated from the BNC samples by exposure to a cellulase solution (37.5 U/ml, pH 6.5) for 3 h. The number of cells obtained by cultivation on BNC_PM greatly exceeded the number of cells obtained from unmodified BNC. The approaches presented here may be useful for the preparation of (1) degradable BNC scaffolds for tissue engineering and (2) continuous scaffold-free cell sheets applicable in wound healing.

1. Introduction

Cellulases are among the most abundant enzymes in the world. In nature, they are produced by fungi, bacteria and protozoa. These enzymes break down cellulose into glucose and thus represent an important part of the chemical processes occurring in nature [1–3]. The cellulase enzyme system consists of three main parts: β -glucosidase, *endo*-1,4- β -D-glucanase (endoglucanase) and *exo*-1,4- β -D-glucanase (exoglucanase). Endoglucanase acts on inner sites of amorphous cellulose, while exoglucanase hydrolyzes non-reducing ends of crystalline cellulose to form cellobiose or glucose, and β -glucosidase acts on non-reducing ends of cellobiose and cellodextrin [4]. Cellulases have an indispensable place in the industrial field, where they require higher activity and stability in order to withstand various harsh conditions.

Microbial cellulases isolated from marine environments have the ability to withstand extreme pH, temperature, and salinity, e.g. cellulase produced by *Gracilibacillus* sp. *SK1*, *Bacillus halodurans* CAS 1 or *Aspergillus ZJUBE-1* has the ability to withstand 60 °C. These enzymes were commercialized in the 1960 s, and in the global enzyme market, cellulases are the third most important industrial enzymes (~15 %), after amylase (~25 %) and protease (~18 %).

Cellulases have found applications in various industrial sectors, such as the food, paper, textile, and biofuel industries, as well as in agriculture [4,5]. Their application has also been explored in various biomedical fields. They have been used for the treatment of infections caused by microorganisms encapsulated in a cyst that is partially made of cellulose. This cyst causes antibiotic treatment failure, which could be reduced or eliminated by the use of cellulases [6,7]. In tissue

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: Lubica.Stankova@fgu.cas.cz (L. Stankova), Lucie.Bacakova@fgu.cas.cz (L. Bacakova).

¹ Both authors contributed equally.

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Table 1
Visual assessment of dBNC sample degradation.

Amount of cellulase	1 day	2 days	3 days	5 days	7 days	9 days	14 days
0.3 U/mg							
0.6 U/mg							
1.2 U/mg							
1.5 U/mg							

no visual change;
 the sample did not lose its integrity, but small pieces were floating in the solution;
 the sample lost its integrity and broke into larger pieces;
 the sample was broken into smaller pieces;
 almost no visible pieces in the solution.

engineering, the effect of cellulases has been applied in several ways. In a study by Tamo et al. (2022), a 3D-printed cellulose-based biomaterial with cellulase encapsulated in chitosan-caseinate nanoparticles was prepared. The enzyme was slowly released from these nanoparticles, which led to gradual colonization of the biomaterial by cells [8]. The application of cellulases can also include tailoring the porosity of biomaterials. For example, cellulases were applied to control the porosity of injectable gelatin-hydroxyphenylpropionic acid/carboxymethylcellulose-tyramine (Gtn-HPA/CMC-Tyr) porous hydrogel, and *in vivo* tests on rats showed no pathological reactions within the implants or in the subcutaneous tissue where the biomaterial was injected [9]. Particularly interesting is the use of cellulase to prepare scaffold-free cell structures, e.g. free-standing cell sheets or multicellular 3D tissue constructs.

Tissue engineering uses cell scaffolds to support anchorage-dependent cells to adhere, proliferate and form structures of desired shapes (for a review, see [10]). After successful cultivation, it is necessary for the scaffolds to be removed and for the desired cell structures to be recovered in an intact state. Conventional methods for detaching cells from their growth supports using proteolytic enzymes (e.g. trypsin, collagenase) result in disruption of the extracellular matrix and cell-cell junctions, and disintegration of the multicellular structure into a suspension of single cells [11,12]. Currently-used degradable synthetic polymer scaffolds, such as polylactides or poly(lactide-co-glycolide), generate acidic byproducts with potentially adverse effects on cells. However, the use of cellulose as a scaffold provides us with a unique opportunity to obtain the desired cellular structures using cellulase enzymes, which do not degrade mammalian tissues and result in the degradation of cellulose to glucose, a natural nutrient for cells [13].

Cellulases have been used to degrade e.g. regenerated cellulose [14,15], carboxymethylcellulose [11] or cellulose acetate [13]. In these studies, continuous sheets of endothelial cells [15], fibroblasts [11] or even mature and functionally-competent cardiac cell networks [13] were formed on top of cellulose-based cell scaffolds, and the scaffolds were degraded using cellulase solutions. A similar technique has also been used to create a pre-vascularized 3D smooth muscle tissue on regenerated cellulose hollow fibers [14]. However, the degradation rate of cellulose depends on the crystallinity, surface area, degree of polymerization or porosity of the cellulose sample [16]. It is therefore necessary to investigate the degradation ability and degradation rate of every form of potential cellulose-based cell scaffold.

Bacterial nanocellulose (BNC), a natural polysaccharide produced by cultivation of *Komagataeibacter sucrofermentans* species, is a promising material with great potential to be used as a cell scaffold, especially in skin tissue engineering and wound dressing. Although the chemical composition of BNC is identical to that of commonly used plant cellulose, it has much higher crystallinity, mechanical strength and swelling

in water, due to its nanofibrous structure [17,18]. BNC bioactivity can be further enhanced by modifying its physicochemical surface properties, such as wettability, porosity, chemical composition, or by preparing BNC-based composites with bioactive substances such as collagen or hydroxyapatite [19]. In our previous work, we investigated the adhesion, proliferation, metabolic activity and phenotypic maturation of human keratinocytes, dermal fibroblasts and endothelial cells, i.e. cell types important for the healing of skin defects, on BNC modified by two different types of drying techniques followed by plasma modification (PM). In short, we found that air-drying (AD) usually leads to better results compared to lyophilization (L), and that PM can further improve cell behavior [20,21].

However, the function of controlled degradability still needs to be introduced into BNC scaffolds. This function can be achieved either by direct incorporation of cellulases into the BNC-based material or by secondary exposure to a solution containing cellulases to obtain scaffold-free cell structures, e.g. free-standing cell sheets. In this work, cellulase from *Trichoderma reesei* (1) was incorporated into BNC and the degradation time was studied, (2) was used in solutions for studies of BNC degradation, and (3) was used to generate continuous sheets of human keratinocytes, applicable in skin tissue engineering and active wound healing, from variously dried BNC scaffolds with or without PM.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Preparation of BNC foils

BNC was produced by *Komagataeibacter sucrofermentans* (Leibniz-Institut DSMZ, Braunschweig, Germany, DSM 15973). Cultivation was carried out in Hestrin-Schramm culture medium [22], consisting of glucose (20 g/L), disodium hydrogen phosphate dodecahydrate (6.8 g/L), special peptone (5 g/L), yeast extract (5 g/L), and citric acid monohydrate (1.3 g/L); pH 5.8. Cultivation lasted for at least 21 days at 28 °C in Erlenmeyer flasks under static conditions. Purification of the BNC from bacteria and a medium residue was performed by rinsing in boiling 0.1 M NaOH twice and then rinsing in boiling distilled water until the BNC was completely clean. To completely remove the bacterial residues, the samples were washed in a 10 % (m/m) solution of SDS and trypsin solution. The washed BNC hydrogels were solidified by air drying (AD) on PTFE foils (to prevent sticking to the surface) or by lyophilization (L) in an Alpha 3–4 LSC basic freeze dryer (Christ, Osterode am Harz, Germany) for at least 24 h.

2.2. Plasma-modification of BNC foils

The surface of the solid samples was modified in a direct current

(glow, diode) Ar⁺ plasma discharge on a Balzers SCD 050 device (BALTEC, Balzers, Lichtenstein). The conditions were set as follows: gas purity of 99.997 %, Ar pressure of 7 Pa, electrode distance of 55 mm, electrode area of 48 cm², chamber volume of approx. 1 dm³, plasma volume of 0.24 dm³, electrical current of 12 mA, and voltage of 750 V. The samples were modified from both sides for 240 s.

2.3. Preparation of degradable BNC (dBNC) samples

Circular samples with a diameter of 16 mm and a weight of approx. 4 mg were cut out from lyophilized BNC (BNC_L) foils. The cellulase solution was prepared by dissolving 5 mg of the cellulase powder (Sigma Aldrich, cellulase from *Trichoderma reesei* ATCC 26921, Cat. No. C8546, $c_U = 5$ U/mg) in 1 ml of distilled water. Different amounts of this solution were then dripped onto each sample and were subsequently air-dried on PTFE foils to obtain samples with a different cellulase content (Table 1). To evaluate the cellulase content, the samples were weighed before dripping (m_0) and after air-drying (m_1), and the cellulase content was calculated according to the following equation:

$$\text{cellulasecontent} = \frac{(m_1 - m_0) \cdot c_U}{m_1} \quad (1)$$

2.4. Characterization of the BNC samples

The physical and chemical properties of BNC dried by AD or L with or without subsequent PM have been characterized in detail in our previous studies [20,21]. A wide range of methods were used to study chemical composition, surface morphology, wettability, swelling ratio, tensile properties, porosity, and specific surface area.

Here, the chemical composition of BNC-AD, dBNC, and cellulase was measured by Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy (Nicolet iS5 with iD7 attenuated total reflection accessory with diamond crystal, ThermoFisher, Waltham, MA, USA). The spectra were obtained as an average from 128 measurement cycles with a spectral range of 600–4000 cm⁻¹, and 1 cm⁻¹ data interval.

The surface morphology of BNC_AD and dBNC was investigated by scanning electron microscope (SEM) LYRA3 GMU (Tescan, Czech Republic) at 7 kV and 5 kV acceleration and deceleration voltage, respectively. Before the measurement, the samples were sputtered with a thin film of platinum.

2.5. Degradation of dBNC samples

The degradability of dBNC was studied in 2 ml of phosphate-buffered saline (PBS; 0.14 M NaCl, 2.68 mM KCl, 3.16 mM Na₂HPO₄, 1.5 mM KCl, pH = 7.4) with different amounts of glucose (0, 1 %, 2 %, and 4.5 %) or in high-glucose Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM; Thermo Fisher Scientific, Cat. No. 52100021), supplemented with 15 % of fetal bovine serum (FBS; Sebak GmbH, Aidenbach, Germany), at 37 °C under static conditions. The degradation process of the samples was assessed visually after the test tube had been vortexed. To quantify the degradation rate of the samples, the glucose concentration in the buffer solution during incubation was determined by the dinitrosalicylic acid method [23]. The degradation rate was then monitored by the conversion of cellulose to glucose according to the following equation:

$$\text{conversion of cellulose} = \frac{c_{GLC}}{c_{GLCtheor}} \quad (2)$$

where $c_{GLCtheor}$ stands for the theoretical concentration of glucose in the PBS solution if all cellulose was degraded, and c_{GLC} stands for the real concentration of glucose in the PBS solution at a particular time.

These experiments were performed under sterile conditions to avoid any contamination that could reduce the amount of glucose present in the solution. The samples were sterilized by UV germicide light to avoid any deterioration of the cellulase functionality that occurs e.g. during

Table 2

An initial attempt to verify loss of integrity for BNC_AD and BNC_L in cellulase solutions.

BNC	pH	Concentration of cellulase (U/ml)	Time to lost integrity (hours)
AD	6.5	25	3
L	6.5	25	3.5
AD	6.5	37.5	2.5
L	6.5	37.5	3
AD	7.4	37.5	4.5
L	7.4	37.5	5.5

heat sterilization. All experiments were performed in quadruplicates.

2.6. Degradation of BNC samples in cellulase solutions

Circular samples of BNC_AD or BNC_L (diameter 16 mm) were placed in solutions of cellulase dissolved at different concentrations (25 and 37.5 U/ml, Table 2) in 2 ml of standard PBS or in modified PBS with pH adjusted to 6.5 using concentrated HCl, and were incubated at 37 °C under static conditions. The loss of integrity of the samples after vortexing was evaluated visually, and the optimal combination of the cellulase concentration and pH was determined. The BNC_AD or BNC_L samples, either unmodified or plasma-modified, were then soaked in DMEM for one hour, were washed with sterile PBS, and were digested in the cellulase solution with the parameters optimized in the previous step. The degradation was evaluated visually every 30 min. The conversion of cellulose to glucose was determined according to Eq. (2) to see the degradation rate of the BNC samples. These experiments were performed under sterile conditions to avoid any contamination that could reduce the amount of glucose present in the solution. All experiments were performed in quadruplicates.

2.7. Cell model and culture conditions

Human keratinocytes of the HaCaT line, purchased from CLS Cell Lines Service (Eppelheim, Germany), were cultivated in DMEM (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Cat. No. 52100021) with 15 % of FBS (Sebak GmbH, Aidenbach, Germany) and 40 µg/ml of gentamicin (Novartis International AG, Basel, Switzerland). Selected circular BNC samples (BC_AD and BC_L, either unmodified or modified with plasma for 240 s) were sterilized in an autoclave (121 °C, 23 min, 101.3 kPa) and were inserted into the wells of 24-well cell culture polystyrene plates (TPP, Trasadingen, Switzerland). The cells were seeded on the samples at a density of approximately 106,000 cells/cm² (i.e., 200,000 cells/well) into 2 ml of the cell culture medium (mentioned above) per well. The cells were then cultivated for three time periods (1, 3, and 10 days) at 37 °C in a humidified air atmosphere with 5 % CO₂. Tissue culture polystyrene (PS) wells were used as a reference material.

2.8. Evaluation of the cell number, viability and cell island area

Cells on the BNC membranes were cultivated for 1, 3 and 10 days. For each experimental group and time interval, three samples were used, and the experiments were repeated at least three times. On days 1 and 3 after seeding, the cells on the samples were stained by the LIVE/DEAD viability/cytotoxicity kit for mammalian cells (Invitrogen, Molecular Probes, Cat. No. L3224) according to the manufacturer's protocol. Briefly, the cells were incubated in two probes detecting the esterase activity in living cells (calcein AM producing green fluorescence) or detecting the membrane damage in dead cells (ethidium homodimer-1 emitting red fluorescence) for 5 min at 37 °C in a humidified air atmosphere containing 5 % of CO₂. Live and dead cells were then counted on microphotographs taken under an Olympus IX 51 epifluorescence microscope (obj. 4x or 10x) equipped with a DP 70 digital camera. The size of the cell island area was evaluated using ImageJ software on day 1 after seeding.

Fig. 1. FTIR spectra of BNC_AD, dBNC with 0.6 U/mg of cellulase, and cellulase.

On day 10 after seeding, the cells were counted in a Cell Viability Analyzer (Vi-CELL XR, Beckman Coulter). After cellulase degradation, the cell culture was resuspended and the cell number and viability was evaluated. During cell counting, the instrument performs an automatic analysis of the number of viable and dead cells, based on a trypan-blue exclusion test.

2.9. Exposure of cells on BNC to cellulase solution

On day 10 after seeding, the cellulase samples with confluent HaCaT cell layers (BNC_AD) and semi-confluent layers (BNC_L) were transferred from the culture medium to 2 ml PBS of pH 6.5 with cellulase from *Trichoderma reesei* ATCC 26921 (Sigma Aldrich, Cat. No. C8546) of 37.5 units/ml. The samples were incubated for 3 h at 37 °C in a humidified air atmosphere containing 5 % of CO₂. The BNC membranes were visualized under an Olympus IX 51 light microscope (obj. 4x) equipped with a DP 70 digital camera before the cellulase experiment, and then after 1 h and 3 h of incubation in PBS with cellulase.

2.10. Statistical analysis

Quantitative data are presented as the arithmetic mean \pm standard deviation (S.D.) of three independent samples for each experimental

Fig. 3. Conversion of cellulose to glucose (see Eq. (2)) in dBNC samples with various cellulase contents over 14 days of incubation.

group. Data from the cell experiments are presented as violin plots with median and IQR. Statistical significance was evaluated using the One-Way ANOVA, Holm-Sidak method, or using non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis One-Way Analysis of Variance on Ranks, Dunn's method. Values of $p \leq 0.05$ were considered significant. All statistical analyses were performed using SigmaStat 4.0 (Systat Software Inc., USA). Graphs were generated using GraphPad Prism 10 (GraphPad Software, USA).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Degradation of BNC samples with incorporated cellulase

In this work, a cellulase from *Trichoderma reesei* was chosen according to the paper presented by Hu et al. [24]. Although this enzyme is most active at pH 5, it was able to maintain its activity for one month even at a higher pH around 6.5–7, which is required for successful wound healing and for cell growth.

First, degradable samples of BNC (dBNC) with increasing amounts of cellulase (from 0.3 to 1.5 U/ml) were prepared according to the study of Hu and Catchmark [24]. Successful enzyme incorporation into the BNC structure was verified by FTIR spectroscopy (Fig. 1). The spectra of dBNC show characteristic peaks of BNC accompanied by absorption bands of cellulase at wavenumbers of 1540 and 1640 cm^{-1} [25], resulting from its protein structure [4]. SEM images (Fig. 2) also show that dBNC fibers are coated and their pores are filled with a substance, i.e. cellulase, compared to cellulase-free BNC-AD.

Fig. 2. SEM images of BNC_AD and dBNC.

Fig. 4. Cellulose conversion to glucose (see Eq. (2)) of variously aged dBNC samples with a cellulase content of 0.6 U/mg over 14 days of incubation.

The degradability of these samples was tested in PBS to see how they perform under physiological conditions. This was monitored visually (Table 1), and the degradation rate was represented by the conversion of cellulose to glucose calculated according to Eq. (2) (Fig. 3). Although not all samples were completely dissolved, at the conversion around 55 % the samples lost their integrity after vortexing, which can be considered as successful degradation of the scaffold. This was also the maximum conversion rate that we measured due to small pieces of cellulose that were present in the tested solution during the analysis, which devaluated the results that were obtained. Although the cellulase was active at pH 7.4, degradation occurred only during the first 7 days of incubation, after which the cellulase lost its activity. After this time, there was no visual difference between the samples in the solutions that were tested.

The degradation rate of dBNC samples does not depend linearly on the amount of cellulase present. We therefore hypothesized that samples with too high an amount of cellulase would degrade too soon but that samples with too low an amount of cellulase would not degrade at all within the time that cellulase maintains its activity (7 days). Based on our results, we selected the dBNC samples with a cellulase content of 0.6 U/mg as the most promising cell scaffold for tissue engineering, because it was able to support cell growth for at least five days and to degrade and easily separate from the formed tissue.

Next, we tested the ability of dBNC with a cellulase content of 0.6 U/mg to maintain its degradability even after storage for up to 4 weeks. We prepared the dBNC samples and stored them in a closed, dry and dark cabinet for 1 day, 1 week, 2 weeks, and 4 weeks. After these periods, we examined the degradability of these samples in PBS. Similar values of cellulose conversion to glucose were obtained within the error for all differently aged samples (Fig. 4), indicating that the degradability of these samples was maintained up to one month. This is in agreement

with the study of Hu and Catchmark [24], who studied the ability of different cellulases to maintain their activity up to one month. They found that the solution of cellulase from *Trichoderma reesei* stored at 37 °C was able to degrade the same amount of bacterial nanocellulose at each time tested, while the others lost their ability very quickly.

Since the dBNC samples are intended to be used as cell scaffolds in tissue engineering, it is necessary to test their degradability in biological environments. These environments often contain glucose, the end product of cellulose degradation, which could interfere with the degradation of dBNC. For example, it is known that high concentrations of monosaccharides, including glucose, can inhibit the activity of cellulases [26]. Glucose is a molecule commonly found in cell culture media, in cells themselves, and in the extracellular matrix of living tissues. We can hypothesize that if the entire dBNC sample (approximately 4 mg in weight) is degraded and broken down into individual glucose molecules in a buffer without glucose (volume of 2 ml), the final glucose concentration should be 0.2 %. To better understand the role of glucose concentration on the reaction equilibrium of dBNC degradation, dBNC samples were incubated in PBS with different glucose concentrations. In PBS containing up to 2 % glucose, the samples degraded within 1 week, and only in PBS containing 4.5 % glucose did they not degrade (Fig. 5). This indicates that even a tenfold increase in the concentration of glucose in the medium in which dBNC degrades does not affect its ability to degrade.

Based on our finding that dBNC with 0.6 U/mg cellulase degraded even in 2 % glucose solution, we assumed that it would also be able to degrade in DMEM, even high-glucose DMEM containing 4.5 g/L glucose, i.e., 0.45 % glucose solution. Surprisingly, the samples did not degrade and we observed no changes within two weeks. Even dBNC samples with the highest cellulase content (1.5 U/mg), which were cultured in DMEM for one week and then transferred to PBS, did not degrade. This suggests that the ability of cellulase to degrade dBNC is negatively affected by some factor present in the DMEM other than glucose. While PBS is a relatively simple water-based solution containing sodium chloride and potassium chloride in a system of phosphate buffers, namely potassium dihydrogen phosphate and disodium hydrogen phosphate, DMEM is a more complex solution containing a wide range of inorganic salts, amino acids, vitamins, and other compounds that can interfere with the degradation of cellulose by cellulase enzymes. In addition to high concentrations of monosaccharides, including glucose [26], cellulases are known to be inhibited by ferric ions [27], present in DMEM as ferric nitrate, and by phenolic compounds [28], present in the medium as phenol red added as a pH indicator. Supplementation of DMEM with FBS can also significantly affect the activity of cellulases, although more in a positive sense. Bovine serum albumin has been reported to increase the activity of cellulase, probably by increasing its stability and also by blocking the non-specific binding sites for this enzyme [29]. A similar effect has been observed with fibronectin, another important component of blood serum [30]. However, the resulting effect of these proteins on cellulase activity depends on the protein/cellulase ratio [29]. Taken together, this issue requires further investigation.

Fig. 5. One week of incubation of dBNC containing 6 U/mg in PBS with different amount of glucose (0%, 1%, 2%, 4.5%) and DMEM with 15% FBS.

Table 3

Visual assessment of BNC sample degradation.

BNC sample	30 min	60 min	90 min	120 min	150 min	180 min	210 min
BNC_AD							
BNC_AD_PM							
BNC_L							
BNC_L_PM							

no visual change;

the sample did not lose its integrity, but small pieces were floating in the solution;

the sample lost its integrity and broke into larger pieces;

the sample was broken into smaller pieces;

almost no visible pieces in the solution.

3.2. Degradation of BNC samples in cellulase solutions

In tissue engineering, scaffold degradability is required to obtain scaffold-free cell structures, such as free-standing cell sheets. Since the cellulose-loaded (dBNC) samples are not degradable in culture medium, another approach was taken: to prepare scaffolds capable of promoting sufficient cell proliferation and producing confluent cell sheets, and later scaffold degradation without harming the cells. Therefore, four different types of BNC samples were prepared. Never-dried BNC was solidified by either air drying (BNC_AD) or lyophilization (BNC_L). Both groups of these samples were later plasma-modified (PM) to increase their attractiveness for cell colonization.

The physical and chemical properties of the prepared samples have been studied in detail in our previous work [20,21]. Briefly, lyophilization has been shown to be a very mild drying method that results in highly porous materials with an excellent swelling ratio (almost 9000 % of its initial weight) but poor mechanical properties compared to air drying. Subsequent PM results in increased surface roughness, total porosity, specific surface area, surface hydrophilicity, and swelling ratio.

For the degradation of BNC samples by externally added cellulase, we assumed that the cells would be able to survive for some time outside the culture medium, e.g. in PBS, even if the pH of this buffer was slightly lower than physiological. First, we investigated the effect of changing the concentration of cellulase in the buffer in units (U) per ml at two different pH values (6.5 or 7.4), and its influence on the degradability of dried BNC_AD or BNC_L. This initial experiment showed us the time needed for the samples to lose their integrity, after which a continuous cell layer could be removed from the material without any damage (Table 2). Surprisingly, the degradation of BNC_AD samples was 0.5–1 h faster than that of BNC_L, which was not expected. Due to the preserved nanostructure, higher porosity and larger specific surface area measured in our previous work [21], we expected the BNC_L samples to lose integrity faster than the BNC_AD samples, because the enzyme would have access to a greater amount of more loosely intertwined glycosidic bonds. However, this access is only possible in a fully soaked BNC-L structure, because the enzyme is only present in the liquid medium. The time required for full soaking of BNC-AD samples is only one minute, but one hour for BNC-L samples [21], which could explain the faster degradation of BNC_AD samples. Therefore, we think it is very important that the samples are fully swollen before evaluating the degradation time. The water content in the fully swollen sample nanostructure can better maintain the accessibility of the cellulase to the cellulose fibers, thus allowing their degradation.

Based on the results presented in Table 2, we selected the

Fig. 6. Cellulose conversion to glucose of variously dried and subsequently modified BNC samples (BNC_AD – air dried, BNC_AD_PM – air dried plasma modified, BNC_L – lyophilized, and BNC_L_PM – lyophilized plasma modified) in cellulase solution in PBS adjusted to pH to 6.5 and with a cellulase concentration of 37.5 U/ml.

combination of a pH of 6.5 and cellulase concentration of 37.5 U/ml as the best for scaffold removal after cell cultivation. Prior to these cell experiments, we degraded BNC samples, both BNC_AD and BNC_L, with or without subsequent PM, under the mentioned conditions to investigate the reaction rate. The samples were first soaked in DMEM for 1 h to better simulate the condition after cell cultivation, and were then thoroughly washed with sterile PBS to remove any glucose residues that could slow down or even stop the BNC degradation process. Again, the degradation was evaluated visually (Table 3) and by the conversion of cellulose to glucose calculated according to Eq. (2) (Fig. 6).

A visual evaluation showed that the BNC_L samples, when pre-soaked with cell culture medium and thus swollen, degraded faster than the BNC_AD samples (Table 3). The rigid, braided, collapsed nanostructure of BNC_AD, represented by higher tensile strength [21], tightens the BNC fibers close together and does not allow them to separate, even when the chain is degraded. Therefore, the physical release of BNC_AD took longer than the physical release of BNC_L. In addition, the PM samples degraded faster than their non-PM counterparts. Plasma modification can disrupt the polymer chain [31], providing a much higher concentration of chain endings which are more susceptible to exocellulases. As a result, the PM samples lose their

Fig. 7. Morphology of human keratinocytes of the HaCaT line on day 1 and 3 after seeding on BNC samples (AD: air-dried, AD_PM: air-dried plasma-modified, L: lyophilized, L_PM: lyophilized plasma-modified), and in the control polystyrene (PS) wells. Cells were stained using a LIVE/DEAD kit. Viable cells are stained green, dead cells are stained red. Olympus IX 51 epifluorescence microscope, DP 70 digital camera, obj. 10 \times , scale bar 100 μ m. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 8. Number (A, C) and viability (B, D) of human keratinocytes of the HaCaT line on day 1 and 3 after seeding in control polystyrene (PS) wells or on BNC samples (AD: air-dried, AD_PM: air-dried plasma-modified, L: lyophilized, L_PM: lyophilized plasma-modified). Kruskal–Wallis One-Way ANOVA on Ranks, Dunn’s method (A, B, D). One-Way ANOVA, Holm-Sidak method (C). The data distribution is visualized as violin plots, where the dashed central line shows the median, the lower and upper thin dashed lines represent the 1st and 3rd quartiles (Q1 is the 25th percentile, Q3 is the 75th percentile of the sample), and the lower and upper edges of the plot depict the maximum and minimum values. Statistically significant differences among the experimental groups ($p \leq 0.05$) are indicated above the columns by the Roman numerals of the differing groups (all: significantly different from all other groups).

integrity more rapidly (Table 3).

Although the visual assessment showed no signs of degradation until 90 min after the start of incubation, degradation began immediately after this time, as shown in Fig. 6. However, all the samples showed the same degradation rate within the error. This suggests that the glucose is mainly released from the ends of the polymer chains that are located at the edges and on the surface of the sample. The bulk of the cell scaffold, however, retains its mechanical support for cell growth. As mentioned above, at cellulose conversion values higher than 55 %, it was difficult to accurately determine the glucose concentration due to the presence of small pieces of BNC, although some visual changes were still observed. Based on these results we can conclude that the loss of integrity depends not only on the degree of BNC degradation, but also on its nanostructure.

3.3. Cell number, viability and cell island area on BNC samples

On day 1 after seeding, the number of viable HaCaT cells on both BNC_AD and BNC_AD_PM membranes was similar to that on the control

tissue culture polystyrene (PS), whereas the number of viable cells on the lyophilized BNC membranes (BNC_L and BNC_L_PM) was significantly lower than on the control PS. The cell population density on the BNC_L was the lowest, i.e. approximately two times lower than the values on the BNC_AD_PM and the control PS (Figs. 7 and 8A). Cell viability was highest in cells cultured on both BNC_AD membranes and on the plasma-modified BNC_L, ranging from 84 % (BNC_L_PM) to 97 % (BNC_AD_PM) (Fig. 8B). Similar results were obtained in our previous study with normal human dermal fibroblasts (NHDFs) and human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs), where both cell types, especially HUVECs, preferred the mechanically stronger BNC_AD for their adhesion and subsequent growth [21].

The cell preference of both BNC_AD membranes was also evident when the size of the cell island area was measured. The formation of cell islands is a typical phenomenon for keratinocytes during their adhesion and a key factor for the proper formation of a confluent cell layer [32–35]. The cell island area was measured on day 1 of cell cultivation, and it was evident that keratinocytes significantly preferred the surface

Fig. 9. The size of the cell island area of human keratinocytes of the HaCaT line on day 1 after seeding on the BNC samples (AD: air-dried, AD.PM: air-dried plasma-modified, L: lyophilized, L.PM: lyophilized plasma-modified). Cells were stained with a LIVE/DEAD kit, and the cell island area was evaluated using ImageJ software. Kruskal–Wallis One-Way ANOVA on Ranks, Dunn’s method. The data distribution is visualized as violin plots, where the dashed central line shows the median, the lower and upper thin dashed lines represent the 1st and 3rd quartiles (Q1 is the 25th percentile, Q3 is the 75th percentile of the sample), and the lower and upper edges of the plot depict the maximum and minimum values. Statistically significant differences among the experimental groups ($p \leq 0.05$) are indicated above the columns by the Roman numerals of the differing groups (all: significantly different from all other groups).

of both BNC_AD membranes, which was manifested by a significantly higher number and area of cell islands compared to both BNC_L membranes. Microscopic images (Fig. 7) show that the formation of HaCaT islands started earlier on the BNC_AD.PM than on the other BNC samples and that these islands reached a larger size, although this difference is not statistically significant (Fig. 9). It is well known that the material surface properties significantly influence the cell behaviour and the further fate of cells. In addition, the preference for certain material surface properties depends on the specific cell type. For example, while bone cells prefer hard materials with rougher surfaces, cells of skin or vascular origin prefer smoother polymeric surfaces [32–35]. In our previous study, we observed cell type-specific differences in the response to plasma modification of BNC. While this modification improved the adhesion and subsequent growth of NHDFs, its positive effect on HUVECs was less pronounced or was even negative, namely on BNC_L, which became even more swellable and mechanically weaker [21].

Cell adhesion to a material surface is influenced by a number of different physical and chemical factors. Young’s modulus of elasticity is one of the most important factors influencing cell adhesion. As mentioned above, in our experiments, cell adhesion and cell island formation were significantly lower on both BNC_L and BNC.PM compared to the control PS and both types of BNC_AD. According to our previous publication [21], the Young’s modulus of elasticity of BNC_L was 53 ± 13 MPa, while the Young’s modulus of BNC_AD was significantly higher (241 ± 102 MPa). This difference was explained by a higher porosity and swelling ratio of BNC_L. In addition, the results of AFM analysis showed different surface structures, indicating a smoother surface of BNC_AD, which may provide more suitable conditions for the adhesion, spreading and growth of epithelial cells [21].

On the third day of cultivation, there were significant differences in

the cell growth on unmodified and plasma-modified BNC samples. The number of keratinocytes on BNC_AD.PM membranes was similar to that on the control PS, but compared to BNC_AD without plasma modification, the number of cells was significantly higher (more than double). This trend was also observed on the lyophilized BNC, but the difference was not statistically significant. The number of cells on the BNC_L was significantly lower compared to all other samples except BNC_L.PM (Figs. 7 and 8C). The cell viability on the third day of cultivation was above 90 % for all samples except BNC_L, where the cell viability was only around 62 % (Fig. 8D). Taken together, BNC_AD.PM was the most suitable substrate for colonization by HaCaT keratinocytes, which was further confirmed by its ability to promote wound healing as evaluated *in vitro* by a scratch assay (see the [Supplementary Information, Fig. S1](#)).

3.4. Cellulase experiments: cell sheets, effect of cellulase on the cell viability

On day 10 of cultivation, cellulase experiments were performed in order to degrade the BNC membrane and to obtain separate cell sheet layers. A key criterion for these experiments was the formation of a fully confluent cell layer, which was only achieved on the BNC_AD and BNC_AD.PM samples. On the BNC_L and BNC_L.PM samples, the cell population was not fully confluent and the keratinocytes on these surfaces formed islands of different sizes. According to the microscopic images, the BNC_AD, BNC_AD.PM and BNC_L.PM membranes all showed a faster release of the cell sheet layers than BNC_L. This was probably due to the ingrowth of cells into the nanoporous structure of BNC_L. The process of cellulose degradation started from the edges of the membrane and progressed towards the center of the sample. The most promising results were obtained on the BNC_AD.PM, where separate cell sheets were formed and rolled up on both sides of the samples after 3 h of incubation with cellulase (Fig. 10).

The influence of cellulase on the viability of HaCaT cells was analyzed after 3 h of incubation, when the BNC samples were degraded, the population of HaCaT cells was resuspended and the cell number and viability were evaluated in a Vi-CELL XR analyser (Beckman Coulter) using a trypan-blue exclusion test. A positive finding was that the incubation of the cell culture with cellulase did not affect the viability of the HaCaT cells. The experiment was performed with two types of control samples. The first control was the polystyrene culture dish with HaCaT cells without cellulase treatment, and the second control was the HaCaT population on the polystyrene culture dish after 3 h of incubation with cellulase. There was no significant difference in cell viability between the two types of control samples. These results were further confirmed by a scratch assay performed in a confluent layer of HaCaT cells on polystyrene, where the healing of an artificial *in vitro* wound was similar in cells exposed or not exposed to cellulases see the [Supplementary Information, Figs. S2 and S3](#)).

The positive effect of plasma modification on cell adhesion and growth was significant on day 10 of cultivation, where the number of viable HaCaT cells on both BNC_AD.PM and BNC_L.PM was significantly higher than on unmodified BNCs. The cell number of HaCaT cells on the BNC_L.PM was almost 7 times higher than on the BNC_L, and the population of HaCaT cells on the BNC_AD.PM was almost 5 times higher than on the BNC_AD. Moreover, the number of cells on the BNC_AD.PM was significantly higher compared to all samples, including both controls. The number of HaCaTs on the BNC_AD.PM was almost two times higher compared to both types of control samples (Fig. 11).

Similar results in generating viable cell sheets using cellulases added to the culture medium were obtained on carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) seeded with mesenchymal stem cells [36], human corneal limbal epithelial cells [12], fibroblasts [11] and endothelial cells [15]. The attractiveness of CMCs for cell colonization was enhanced by conjugating them with dopamine, which also ensures their adhesiveness to the surface of the culture dishes [12,36], as well as by conjugating them

Fig. 10. Morphology of populations of human keratinocytes of the HaCaT line on day 10 after seeding on BNC samples (AD: air-dried, AD_PM: air-dried plasma-modified, L: lyophilized, L_PM: lyophilized plasma-modified). Δ – cell population layer; * – beginning of cell sheet separation; + – degrading BNC. Olympus IX 51 microscope, DP 70 digital camera, obj. 4 \times , scale bar 200 μ m.

with tyramine [11] or coating them with fibronectin [15]. On the one hand, our system has the advantage of using only physical modifications of cellulose (i.e. plasma treatment preceded by air drying or lyophilization) without the addition of foreign molecules, especially cross-linking and coupling agents. On the other hand, in our study, the BNC cell sheets did not start to peel until after 3 h of exposure to cellulase, whereas in the studies by other authors, peeling took place already after 5–10 min [11,36] or after at least 1 h [12] or after 1.5 h [15]. However, these studies usually used higher concentrations of cellulase, such as 50 U/ml [36] or even 100 U/ml [12]. Only the study by Ko et al. [15] used a similar cellulase concentration (8 mg/ml) as in our study (7.5 mg/ml, 37.5 U/ml), and the study by Sakai et al. [11] used as little as 5 U/ml.

In this context, it should be noted that the studies by Ko et al. [15] and Sakai et al. [11] used CMC, which is water-soluble and is less crystalline than BNC, and is therefore more susceptible to degradation than BNC. In addition, different authors used cellulases from different sources, which may have differed in the number of units per mg and therefore in their degradative activity. Finally, the effect of cellulase is also cell type-specific. In a study by Entcheva et al. [13], cardiac fibroblasts were more sensitive than cardiomyocytes to this enzyme. When treated for 24 h with 23, 46 or 92 units of cellulase, fibroblasts detached from cellulose acetate scaffolds at 46 and 92 units, whereas cardiomyocytes maintained their macroscopic integrity at all doses [13].

To further improve the cell sheet technology, some studies by other authors have used a polymeric cell shifter membrane to facilitate the transfer of the intact cell sheet onto a fresh cell culture substrate [12,15]. Nevertheless, to the best of our knowledge, our study is the first to use modified BNC to produce continuous, free-standing cell sheets. A study by Lamboni et al. successfully cultured intestinal neurons and smooth muscle cells on microstructured bacterial cellulose, making a first step towards the production of cell sheets that could be used to regenerate the intestinal muscular layer. However, actual production of cell sheets was not realized [37].

Cellulases can also be incorporated into the interior of 3D cellulose-based materials (including bioinks for 3D bioprinting) for their controlled degradation, for example by immobilizing them in a gelatin additive to BNC [38] or by encapsulating them in chitosan-caseinate nanoparticles incorporated into chitosan hydrogels reinforced with cellulose nanofibers of plant origin [8]. In these systems, the cellulose component of the material slowly and gradually degraded over the next 2–4 weeks, while allowing the adhesion and growth of fibroblasts. When 3D smooth muscle tissue was grown on regenerated hollow cellulose fibers and then exposed to cellulase added to the culture medium (8 mg/ml, pH 7.0), which was exchanged every 24 h, the degradation of the fibers took 2 days [14].

Fig. 11. Number (A) and viability (B) of human keratinocytes of the HaCaT line on day 10 of cultivation and after 3 h of cellulase treatment, in control polystyrene (PS) wells, or on BNC samples (AD: air-dried, AD_PM: air-dried plasma-modified, L: lyophilized, L_PM: lyophilized plasma-modified). PS* – control polystyrene without cellulase treatment. One-Way ANOVA, Holm-Sidak method (A). Kruskal–Wallis One-Way ANOVA on Ranks, Dunn’s method (B). The data distribution is visualized as violin plots, where the dashed central line shows the median, the lower and upper thin dashed lines represent the 1st and 3rd quartiles (Q1 is the 25th percentile, Q3 is the 75th percentile of the sample), and the lower and upper edges of the plot depict the maximum and minimum values. Statistically significant differences among the experimental groups ($p \leq 0.05$) are indicated above the columns by the Roman numerals of the differing groups (all: significantly different from all other groups).

4. Conclusion and further perspectives

In this study, we aimed to convert bacterial nanocellulose (BNC) into a bioactive and degradable cell carrier applicable in skin tissue engineering and wound healing. Bioactivity, i.e., attractiveness for cell adhesion and growth, was achieved by plasma modification preceded by air drying or lyophilization. Degradability was achieved in two ways:

- (1) Cellulase was incorporated directly into the structure of the BNC samples in four different concentrations. The degradation rate, monitored by measuring the glucose emerging from the reaction of cellulase with dBNC samples, was found to be proportional to the cellulase concentration. The most promising samples contained 0.6 U/mg of cellulase, because they were able to maintain their integrity for at least 5 days (allowing the cells to grow) while degrading within 1 week. We also proved cellulase activity of dBNC samples up to 1 month, where we obtained the same degradation curves. These results suggest that cellulase-loaded BNC is a promising material for tissue engineering, where we expect gradual replacement of the material scaffold by newly-regenerated tissue.
- (2) The other way was to treat the BNC samples after 10 days of HaCaT cell cultivation with cellulase solution of 37.5 U/ml at pH 6.5. Under these conditions, BNC loses its integrity within 3 h. The HaCaT cells were found to be able to withstand these conditions and to maintain their viability. PM was found to be particularly beneficial in this case, as it increases the cyto-compatibility of the substrates and also improves the degradation process, allowing for efficient separation of the confluent cell sheets. This leads to a significant increase in the number of HaCaT cells after they have been separated from the BNC substrate in the case of the BNC_L_PM and especially the BNC_AD_PM samples after 10 days of cultivation. This method was able to produce scaffold-free continuous sheets of HaCaT cells, and is therefore promising for cell sheet technology in regenerative medicine, e.g. skin tissue engineering and active wound healing.

Data availability

The data presented in this study are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15497960>, and are also available on request from the corresponding author.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Lubica Stankova: Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Anna Kutova:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Martina Doubkova:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Ondrej Kvitek:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Antonin Sedlar:** Visualization. **Vaclav Svorcik:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Lucie Bacakova:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2025.114111>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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